

Structure refinement and impedance properties of polycrystalline orthorhombic yttrium substituted calcium titanate $\text{Ca}_{1-x}\text{Y}_x\text{TiO}_{3+\delta}$ ($x = 0.1-0.3$)

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Abstract : Perovskite ceramic phases with composition $\text{Ca}_{1-x}\text{Y}_x\text{TiO}_{3+\delta}$ (where $x = 0.1, 0.2$ and 0.3 ; hereafter CYT-10, CYT-20 and CYT-30) have been synthesized by solid state reaction at 1050°C . The structure refinement using General Structure Analysis System (hereafter GSAS) software converges to satisfactory profile indicators such as Rietveld parameters : R_p , R_{wp} , RF^2 and goodness of fit. The title phases crystallize at room temperature in the space group Pbnm (#62) with $a = 5.3741(4) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 5.4300(4) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 7.6229(5) \text{ \AA}$ and $Z = 4$. Major inter atomic distances, bond angles and structure factors have been calculated from the step analysis data of the compound. The crystal morphology has been examined by scanning electron microscopy. Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis of the specimens show that yttrium enters into the structural framework of CaTiO_3 . The particle size of the ceramic phases along major reflecting planes ranges between 12–40 nm. The polyhedral (CaO_8 and TiO_6) distortions and valence calculations from bond strength data are also reported. The Nyquist plots show the presence of both grain ($>10^2$ Hz) and the grain boundary ($<10^2$ Hz) effects in the materials. The ceramic phases CYT-10 and CYT-20 show enhanced frequency dependent and almost temperature independent dielectric constants.

Keywords : Perovskites, powder X-ray diffraction, Rietveld refinement, impedance nanoceramic.

Introduction

Perovskite type oxides of general formula ABO_3 are well known for their property of cationic substitution on A site¹⁻⁴. Such materials have received attention due to their variety of applications in making electronic devices. They dominate the low and medium permittivity range of microwave dielectrics and temperature stable ceramics providing high quality factor⁵⁻⁷.

Moreover, the versatility of perovskite structure opens up possibility of making solid solutions designed to achieve specific requirements. CaTiO_3 has been also identified as a potential material for long term immobilization of radioactive cations such as trivalent actinides (Cm^{3+} , Am^{3+} , Pu^{3+}) and rare earth (Gd^{3+} , La^{3+}) cations. Immobilization of Sr^{2+} , U^{4+} , Y^{3+} and Ba^{2+} has also been reported in CaTiO_3 , which is one of the major constituents of synthetic rock (synroc) assemblage⁸⁻¹⁰. To understand the mechanism of immobilization of Y^{3+} ion in CaTiO_3 through crystallochemical interaction, a detailed study of yttrium substituted calcium titanate of composition $\text{Ca}_{1-x}\text{Y}_x\text{TiO}_3$ ($x = 0.1, 0.2$ and 0.3) have been undertaken.

Results and discussion

All prominent reflections of the X-ray diffraction patterns of the $\text{Ca}_{1-x}\text{Y}_x\text{TiO}_{3+\delta}$ ($x = 0.1, 0.2$ and 0.3) have been indexed for orthorhombic system constrained by operators of space group Pbnm (#62). In samples CYT-10, CYT-20 and CYT-30 the intensity and positions of all major reflections match with those of parent perovskite structure of CaTiO_3 ¹¹ (Fig. 1). However, in CYT-30 traces of minor secondary phases of CaY_4O_7 ($d = 2.94 \text{ \AA}$) and Y_2O_3 ($d = 3.06 \text{ \AA}$) have been also observed (peaks * marked). The Rietveld refinement of crystal data of phase pure CYT-10 was performed by the least square method using GSAS software¹² (Fig. 2a). The reflection conditions for the chosen space group were verified from the international table for X-ray crystallography and checked by presence of 021 and absence of 201 reflections¹³⁻¹⁶. Other systematically absent reflections in support of chosen space group were also verified by Intensity Statistics (ISTATS) software. In addition to these, both odd-odd-odd and odd-odd-even reflections are present in the title phase indicating that the oxygen octahedra are tilted both in phase as well as anti phase¹⁷.

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffraction patterns of $\text{Ca}_{1-x}\text{Y}_x\text{TiO}_{3+\delta}$ ($x = 0.1, 0.2$ and 0.3) ceramic phases along with the indexed reflections.

Figs. 2. (a) Rietveld refinement plot for $\text{Ca}_{0.90}\text{Y}_{0.10}\text{TiO}_{3+\delta}$ ceramic sample showing observed (+), calculated (continuous line) and difference (lower) curves. The vertical bars denote Bragg reflections of the crystalline phase. (b) Probability plot between $I_0 - I_C$ for polycrystalline $\text{Ca}_{0.90}\text{Y}_{0.10}\text{TiO}_{3+\delta}$ ceramic sample.

The normal probability plot for the histogram gives nearly a straight line indicating that the I_0 and I_C values are for the most part normally distributed with a slope of 1.2059 (Fig. 2b). The crystal data was derived from the crystal information file prepared after final cycle of refinement by Rietveld analysis¹⁸. The accuracy of the fit is indicated by agreement in the expected and calculated R -factors and goodness of fit (Table 1). The final refinement was carried out with occupancies constrained at $\text{Ca} = 90\%$ and $\text{Y} = 10\%$ which matches with the composition of the representative sample of the ceramic powder. The atomic coordinates, isotropic thermal parameters, major inter-atomic distances and angles data along with polyhedral distortions ' Δ ',^{19,20} are summarized in Tables 2 and 3. The inter-planar spacing and their observed and calculated structure factors have been also determined. The inter-atomic distances between Ti(1) and the apex oxygen atoms of the octahedron have been found to be 2.05434 Å whereas the two sets of planar oxygen bond distances Ti(1)-O(5) are 1.90487 and 2.01256 Å respectively (Fig. 3). For the given coordination number the calculated M-O distances are close to their standard values of metal oxygen distances in corresponding metal oxides²¹. The DIAMOND projection of the crystal model represents appropriately the coordination spheres of Ca

Table 1. Crystallographic data for polycrystalline $\text{Ca}_{0.9}\text{Y}_{0.1}\text{TiO}_{3+\delta}$ at room temperature

Structure	Orthorhombic
Space group	Pbnm (#62)
Lattice parameters	$a = 5.3741(4) \text{ \AA}$ $b = 5.4300(4) \text{ \AA}$ $c = 7.6229(5) \text{ \AA}$ $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90.0$
Z	4
R_{wp}	0.2421
R_p	0.1735
wR expected	0.1899
RF^2	0.15122
Volume of unit cell	222.449(16) \AA^3
Unit cell formula weight	565.523
Density χ -ray	4.222
Goodness of fit (S)	1.28
D_{wd}	1.366
Slope	1.2022

Table 2. Final refined lattice parameters, atomic coordinates and Rietveld parameters of CYT-10 phase at room temperature

Atom	x	y	z	Occupancy	$U_{iso} (\text{\AA}^2)$
Ti(1)	0.00	0.50	0.0	1.00	0.01847
Ca(2)	0.97535	0.02271	0.25	0.9130	0.01159
Y(3)	0.97535	0.02271	0.25	0.10	0.01159
O(4)	0.1240	0.430	0.25	1.0	0.01866
O(5)	0.7106	0.3029	0.03325	1.0	0.01866

Table 3. Selected interatomic distances (\AA), O–M–O angles and polyhedral distortions for CYT-10 phase

Ca/Y–O(4)	2.35144(16)	Ca/Y–Ca/Y	4.01067(21)*2
Ca/Y–O(4)	2.21120(15)	Ca/Y–Ca/Y	3.82860(23)*2
Ca/Y–O(5)	2.65877(11)*2	Ca/Y–Ca/Y	3.63838(19)*2
Ca/Y–O(5)	2.27007(9)*2	Ti–O(4)	2.05435(11)*2
Ca/Y–O(5)	2.67528(12)*2	Ti–O(5)	2.01255(11)*2
Ca/Y–Ti	3.42131(19)*2	Ti–O(5)	1.90487(10)*2
Ca/Y–Ti	3.21965(17)*2	Ca/Y–Ti	3.18949(16)*2
Ca/Y–Ti	3.40539(18)*2		
Bond angles (deg.) :			
O(4)–Ti–O(4)	180.0(0)	O(4)–Ca–O(5)	130.6439(18)*2
O(4)–Ti–O(5)	92.1466(25)*2	O(4)–Ca–O(4)	107.9959(28)*2
O(4)–Ti–O(5)	102.5210(20)*2	O(4)–Ca–O(5)	67.6926(26)*2
O(4)–Ti–O(5)	87.8534(25)*2	O(5)–Ca–O(5)	93.412(5)
O(4)–Ti–O(5)	77.4789(20)*2	O(5)–Ca–O(5)	121.172(4)
O(5)–Ti–O(5)	89.041(5)*2	O(5)–Ca–O(5)	67.231(5)*2
O(5)–Ti–O(5)	180.000(0)	O(5)–Ca–O(5)	123.497(4)*2
O(5)–Ti–O(5)	90.959(5)*2	O(5)–Ca–O(5)	63.178(4)*2

Table-3 (contd.)

O(5)–Ti–O(5)	179.9657(0)	O(5)–Ca–O(5)	121.172(4)*2
O(4)–Ca–O(5)	83.2992(32)	O(5)–Ca–O(5)	76.842(4)
O(4)–Ca–O(5)	69.121(4)*2	O(5)–Ca–O(5)	168.9843(6)*2
O(4)–Ca–O(5)	130.0958(21)*2	O(5)–Ca–O(5)	78.855(4)*2
O(4)–Ca–O(5)	60.4322(17)*2		
Polyhedral distortions (\AA)	CaO_8	TiO_6	
$\Delta (\times 10^4)$	52.80	10.01	

$\Delta = 1/n \sum \{(R_i - R_m)/(R_m)\}^2$ where $n = 8$ and 6 for eight and six coordination respectively, *indicates the multiplicity of bond, figures in parenthesis show the esd values.

Fig. 3. ORTEP view of Ti coordination in TiO_6 with their respective bond lengths.

and Ti atoms (Fig. 4). The B-site of the perovskite maintains six coordinations with the shortest Ti–O(5) bond of 1.90487 \AA and the longest one Ti–O(4) of 2.05434 \AA . The distortion of TiO_6 species reduces the coordination number of Ca/Y atoms to 8 resulting into eight acentric bonds in contrast to twelve for ideal cubic perovskite. The geometry of Ca/Y coordination sphere defined by the tilted octahedra is, therefore, a distorted cuboctahedron in relation to ideal A-site polyhedron in cubic perovskite, which has four triangular, and six square faces²². The bond valence ($V_i = \sum b_{ij}$ where $b_{ij} = (R_o/R)^N$)²³ for Ca was found to be significantly high confirming residual compression of Ca–O bonds. The compression of the Ca cation is primarily attributed to the partial occupancy by the marginally smaller cation (Y^{3+}) in the perovskite framework. In addition, the displacement of the Ca cation due to octahedral tilting also contributes to the compression

Fig. 4. DIAMOND projection of sticks and ball representation of coordination sites of Ti and Ca/Y

of the A-site species. The oxidation state for Ti^{4+} has been found to be 4.08, which is consistent with the expected formal oxidation state of titanium in B-site of perovskite structure. The rare-earths and trivalent actinides preferentially replace Ca^{2+} where charge balance is achieved by partial replacement or substitution of Ti^{4+} by Ti^{3+} ^{24,25}. However, the mechanism of substitution of Ca^{2+} by Y^{3+} in perovskite solid solution needs explanation in terms of charge balance. One of the plausible mechanisms could be the charge compensation through change in perovskite sub stoichiometry i.e. by increase of oxygen content. Within the permissible statistical limits, the EDX analysis shows consistency in observed and theoretical atomic and weight ratios with respect to Y and Ti.

Phase	Y/Ti weight ratio	Y/Ti atomic ratio
CYT-10	0.16 (Calcd. 0.18)	0.09 (Calcd. 0.10)
CYT-20	0.39 (Calcd. 0.37)	0.21 (Calcd. 0.20)

The EDX spectra show the presence of yttrium in the polycrystalline phases (Fig. 5a). The scanning electron micrographs show the typical morphology of the grains, which are about of 0.2–0.3 μm in length (Fig. 5b). The particle size calculation has been done for most of the low angle and high intensity reflections using Scherer's

formula²⁶ (Table 4). The size distribution along the reflection planes ranges from 12–40 nm for $Ca_{1-x}Y_xTiO_{3+\delta}$ ($x = 0.1-0.3$) ceramic phases. The electron density map (Fourier map) of CYT-10 constructed in order to locate atoms viz. Ca/Y, Ti and O reflects the form of sliced sections through the structure at regular intervals wherein the peak height is proportional to the number of electrons possessed by particular atom (Fig. 6). The relative peak heights with respect to Ca and Ti at different locations have been found 1.0 ± 0.05 against the expected value of 1.0. The Fourier plot that shows contour maps of calcium and titanium has three minimum values of charge density between Ti and O atoms due to presence of three different Ti–O distances in the crystal (0.264, 0.128 and 0.085 electrons per a.u.³). The Ti–O bond is covalent with some partial ionic character. This is due to hybridization effect between Ti-3d and O-2p states²⁷.

Impedance studies :

The surface, interface, grain and grain boundary properties of material can be studied using the complex impedance formalisms, which include the determination of capacitance (bulk and grain boundary), relaxation frequency and electronic conductivity. A polycrystalline phase

Fig. 5. (a) EDAX spectra and (b) SEM images of polycrystalline $\text{Ca}_{1-x}\text{Y}_x\text{TiO}_{3+\delta}$ ($x = 0.1$ and 0.2) ceramic powders.

Table 4. Distribution of particle size along prominent reflections of $\text{Ca}_{1-x}\text{Y}_x\text{TiO}_{3+\delta}$ ($x = 0.1-0.3$) phases

h, k, l planes	CYT-10		CYT-20		CYT-30	
	FWHM (2θ)	Particle size (nm)	FWHM (2θ)	Particle size (nm)	FWHM (2θ)	Particle size (nm)
0 0 2	0.20	40.60	0.24	33.83	0.22	36.90
1 1 1	0.20	40.82	0.36	22.68	0.28	29.15
2 0 0	0.22	37.73	0.28	29.64	0.24	34.56
2 1 1	0.26	32.48	0.30	28.15	0.58	14.55
0 0 4	0.26	33.45	0.32	27.17	0.28	31.03
3 1 2	0.70	13.10	0.60	15.27	0.72	12.71
2 2 4	0.42	23.07	0.44	22.02	0.44	22.00
4 2 0	0.64	16.17	0.58	17.84	0.70	14.75

usually gives grain and grain boundary properties with different time constants leading to two successive semi-circles. The electrical properties of a material are often represented in terms of some complex parameters like complex permittivity ϵ^* , complex impedance Z^* , electric

Fig. 6. Calculated Fourier map showing contours of charge density of $\text{Ca}_{0.90}\text{Y}_{0.10}\text{TiO}_{3+\delta}$ ceramic powder.

modulus M^* and loss tangent $\tan \delta$. Nyquist diagram, the plot of Z' (real) versus Z'' (imaginary) is shown in the Fig. 7. The semicircle shows that there is a depression angle instead of a semicircle centered on the real axis.

constant of 10 mole% yttrium doped material is higher than the corresponding ϵ' value for CaTiO_3 ²⁹. At lower frequencies there is substantial dielectric loss but the loss decreases sharply with increase in frequency and reduces

Fig. 7. Impedance spectrum of $\text{Ca}_{1-x}\text{Y}_x\text{TiO}_{3+\delta}$ ($x = 0.1$ and 0.2) ceramic samples.

The behavior of electrical response obeys Cole-Cole formalism²⁸. The shape of the curve suggests that the electrical responses are composed of two semicircles. At low frequencies the grain boundary response is observed but in the high frequency range ($> 10^2$ Hz) the bulk properties of the material dominate in the total value of the electrical response. The depression of the semicircle provides further evidence of polarization phenomena with a distribution of relaxation times.

Dielectric properties of $\text{Ca}_{1-x}\text{Y}_x\text{TiO}_{3+\delta}$ ($x = 0.1$ and 0.2) have been studied as a function of frequency and composition. Yttrium doped calcium titanate exhibits almost temperature independent dielectric constant^{29,30}. The frequency dependence of dielectric constant (ϵ') and tangent loss (δ) at room temperature and 100°C is shown in Figs. 8a and 8b. The decreasing dielectric constant with increasing frequency can be attributed to the lagging of dipoles present in the material which is a typical Debye type behavior exhibited by most of the dielectric material. The calcium titanates with perovskite structures are known to exhibit this type of behavior³¹. The dielectric

to 0.012 after 1×10^5 Hz (Fig. 8b). The variation of ϵ' and $\tan \delta$ may be attributed to hopping of trapped charge carriers, which resulted in an extra dielectric response in addition to dipole response³².

Experimental

Calculated quantities of AR grade CaCO_3 , Y_2O_3 and TiO_2 for the stoichiometry $\text{Ca}_{1-x}\text{Y}_x\text{TiO}_{3+\delta}$ (where $x = 0.1, 0.2$ and 0.3) were thoroughly mixed with 10 ml glycerol medium in a mortar-pestle. The synthesis of the ceramic powder was carried out by repeated grinding and sintering the glycerol paste at 1050°C in a muffle furnace. After 24 h of sintering, densification of materials took place and polycrystalline solid solutions were formed. The powder X-ray diffraction data was recorded on Rigaku RUH3R diffractometer at step size of 0.02° between $2\theta = 5^\circ$ – 90° at counting rate of 2 s/step. In all 4251 data points were subjected to GSAS programming. Scanning electron microscopy and EDX analysis were carried out on Jeol JSM-5600 electron microscope at accelerating voltage of 20 kV.

Fig. 8. Frequency dependence of the dielectric constant and loss for $\text{Ca}_{1-x}\text{Y}_x\text{TiO}_{3+\delta}$ ($x = 0.1$ and 0.2).

Dielectric properties of $\text{Ca}_{0.9}\text{Y}_{0.1}\text{TiO}_{3+\delta}$ has been investigated by a.c. impedance spectroscopy carried out on impedance analyzer HIOKI LCR HITESTER 3532-50 between the frequency range from 42 Hz to 5 MHz. Impedance, capacitance and dissipation factor were collected as a function of frequency in the range of ambient temperature to 140°C over heating and cooling cycles. The

sample in the form of circular disc (1.29 cm diameter and 0.30 cm thickness) was used for measurements after applying silver paint to both electrode surfaces of the pellet.

Conclusions :

The ceramic phase $\text{Ca}_{0.9}\text{Y}_{0.1}\text{TiO}_{3+\delta}$ crystallizes in orthorhombic symmetry. The perovskite matrix of calcium titanate can be modified by partial substitution of

calcium by yttrium to yield a single phase polycrystalline solid solution. The title material has perovskite chains of distorted TiO_6 polyhedrons interlinked through Ca/Y atoms. The particle size along prominent reflection planes lies in the range of 12–40 nm. The crystallographic data and the structure model of the title ceramic phase close to composition $\text{Ca}_{0.9}\text{Y}_{0.1}\text{TiO}_{3+\delta}$ could be useful in the study of structure-property relationship of yttrium loaded nuclear waste forms. The impedance study shows that the material has frequency dependent dielectric constant. At lower frequencies both the dielectric constant and the loss factor is high but the trend is reversed at high frequencies.

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